

A Review on the Impact of Online Job Portals on Employee Performance

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Abstract:

The development of technology in the digital age has had a huge impact on many aspects of our life, including how we find and keep jobs. The introduction of internet job portals has completely changed the way people hunt for jobs by giving them a platform to communicate with businesses. This article examines and assesses the effect of online job portals on worker performance, highlighting the benefits and potential pitfalls of this cutting-edge job search strategy. Now that technology is prevalent everywhere, everything is made simple. Every aspect of human life has been impacted by technology. Thanks to online job portals, where applications are only a click away and hundreds of positions are always open, finding a job has gotten easier nowadays. Job portals offer all varieties of jobs, and the majority of them are free, which increases their popularity in the labour market. Employees hired using online job portals perform as well as those hired through more conventional means. Online job portals are more practical, affordable, time-saving, and accessible. Job portal features like filter, sort by, and generate your resume now are improving the effectiveness of employment portals, something that was previously impossible because it took more time, was less effective, required more personnel, and was less transparent. This study is based on a review of comparable studies to determine the effect of online job portals on employee performance. According to a review of several research studies, online job portals have a favorable effect on employee performance, demonstrating the importance of technology in modern life and how it makes life more efficient and time-saving.

Keywords: Online Job Portal, Technology, Recruitment, Employee, Performance

Introduction

The recruitment process now fully depends upon technology because as the job seekers are increasing and at the same time getting a job is becoming more complex. The recruitment process is to place a candidate at the right position according to his skills and experience. In this time, all the recruitment process is being carried out using technology and internet. Technology has changed the way we live our life, we think, we spend our time, we use gadgets and devices etc. basically our life has changed drastically due to technology. In the same way, the recruitment process has changed, and it has become easier, effective, and cost efficient which has changed the scenario of recruitment totally. Today, a variety of networking websites, such

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as Nakuri.com, Monster.com, Shine.com, Fresher's World, Times Jobs, LinkedIn, Free Jobs Alerts, etc., are used to find qualified candidates for employment. These websites have emerged as significant sources of good personnel for both employees and organizations. Online job portals have a significant impact on employee performance in several ways, making workers more productive because they provide the right guidance regarding market demand for skills, popular job categories, and compensation packages that have an effect on workers' performance. This study is based on the impact of online job portals on employee performance in which related studies have been reviewed to know the impact. From the review of various research papers, it is found that the positive impact of online job portals on employee performance which shows the technology is playing a vital in human life and more technology is making life easy and effective and saving the precious time. E-recruitment is a method that handles the full hiring process, from beginning to end, including posting job ads, receiving resumes, and choosing the best candidate for the job based on their qualifications. It functions effectively and efficiently. The ability to attract quality candidates (in terms of abilities, attitude, knowledge, and aptitudes) for the company is aided by the use of the internet.

Literature review

Recruitment

Edwin B. Flippo (1984) It studied that Recruitment is the main duty of the human resource department. Finding, enticing, screening, reducing the field, interviewing, selecting, hiring, and onboarding employees are all steps in the process. "Recruitment is the process of seeking out potential employees and encouraging them to submit applications for positions within the firm."

Parry & Wilson (2009) Determine that "recruitment encompasses those processes and actions conducted by the organization with the primary goal of identifying and recruiting potential personnel." The size of the recruitment team of a company might vary depending on the size of the organization. In smaller businesses, a recruiting manager, however, is frequently in charge of recruiting. Many organizations outsource their hiring needs, but some merely use advertisements, job Portals to identify candidates for open positions. To improve and streamline the hiring process, many businesses employ hiring software nowadays.

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The basis of a successful recruitment process is an organization-specific sourcing model that aims to find the best applicant for the ideal role at the ideal moment. It is a methodical process for enlisting outstanding individuals who can super business expansion. The five main stages of an all-encompassing hiring process might differ from company to firm depending on the business vertical, organizational structure, size, operational style, and selection procedure

E-Recruitment Process

E-Recruitment is the rage right now and represents the newest trends in hiring. The use of technology or web-based solutions to facilitate the hiring process is also referred to as "online recruitment." The resource may be an employment website like naukri.com, the company's official website, or its own intranet. The internet is being used by both large and small businesses as a source of hiring.

“E-recruiting is using the internet to recruit through Job portals, corporate websites, specialized websites or online advertisement”, Galanaki (2002).

The organization's e-recruitment initiatives and e-recruitment process have an impact on the structure, effectiveness, and efficiency of the organization's recruiting process. The HR division oversees the diversity of the workforce with regard to culture, time zones, specializations, benefits, and salary. Secondary data was collected for this study. According to this study, employers seem to more concerned about hiring a qualified, quality-oriented candidate over one who is more concerned with price. Third parties, such as headhunters and recruiting agencies, actively participate in the online hiring process. E-recruitment improves efficiency and efficacy of the hiring process. Particular internet recruitment techniques contribute to organizational advancements and improve organizational recruiting performance. Fred and Kinange (2016). Most of the organizations in Pakistan were using both e-recruitment and traditional recruitment sources. It also revealed that the IT based organizations are not completely relying on e-recruitment. The study also indicated that majority of respondent organizations use e-recruitment for filling the top positions Nasreem et al. (2016)

Online Job Portals

Job portals are a straightforward but useful tool. They make room for both companies and

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employees and make it simpler to access a wide range of employment in various industries and skill levels. They also lower fees for middlemen and headhunters as well as the costs of job matching. Job websites have improved employment access for all people. Before they existed, informal networks and social contacts dominated the job-seeking landscape. Social network job searches typically favor well-connected individuals, further entrenching already-existing inequities. This implicit prejudice in access to both official and informal jobs can be lessened by ensuring equal access to online job platforms. The Covid-19 pandemic, which harmed every industry area, had an effect on every firm in the world. In April to May 2021, there were around 22.7 million job losses, according to research by the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy. As the life is being normal, so the hiring process in India has surged apparently, especially last August has witnessed 89 percent increase and hiring for specific roles has grown as well specially in IT sector. According to estimates, the largest employment portals fill more than 80% of job advertisements. In that time job portals play a vital role in recruitment process.

Employee Performance

A worker's performance is defined as how well they carry out their duties and finish vital tasks. It emphasizes the value, quality, and effectiveness of their output. How valuable each individual is to the business depends on their performance. For a business, each person represents a significant investment, therefore the return that Employee contributions must be substantial. Employee performance is influenced by a variety of variables that have an effect on their lives, such as pay, benefits, the workplace culture, bonuses, and admiration.

Impact on Employee Performance

Employee satisfaction is influenced by a variety of factors, including management expectations, coworkers, personal issues, and company culture. Companies must take the initiative to ensure that their staff members are pleased by learning what they need and giving them the resources, they need to improve their talents.

In comparison to individuals who do not use the Internet, the data shows that job searchers who have registered with job portals are about 6% more likely to be employed and that their reservation earnings are 1300 rupees higher (a 10% increase above the mean). Additionally, we discover that employed individuals who are registered with portals have actual incomes that are

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13% greater than those who are not. On the other hand, employees who rely more on social networks for support have slightly lower employment possibilities and lower associated salaries. The impact and role of job portals is vital in the life employee which enables them to perform well and make future bright.

Advantages for Employee Performance

- 1. Increased Access to Opportunities:** Online job boards have democratized the labour market by removing distance restrictions. Job searchers have more options for obtaining work that match their talents and career goals because they can look at opportunities outside of their immediate area. Improved job matching and more job satisfaction may result from this expanded access.
- 2. Efficiency and Speed:** Sending paper applications and waiting for responses was the usual way of looking for work. This procedure has been streamlined by online job portals, which let applicants submit applications in a matter of minutes for several vacancies. This effectiveness shortens the time between searching for a job and getting hired, resulting in smoother transitions and perhaps fewer spells of unemployment.
- 3. Customized Job Search:** Job portals frequently provide search filters that let job seekers focus their search based on particular factors like industry, region, amount of experience, and job type. This personalization enables job seekers to identify positions that closely match their tastes and skill sets, improving the fit between the employee and the employment role.
- 4. Access to Information:** Job portals frequently provide search filters that let job seekers focus their search based on particular factors like industry, region, amount of experience, and job type. This personalization enables job seekers to identify positions that closely match their tastes and skill sets, improving the fit between the employee and the employment role.
- 5. Skill Development:** Candidates frequently need to improve their digital literacy abilities in order to succeed in the digital application process. The ability to use online platforms, build compelling profiles, and submit digital applications might help a job candidate develop skills beyond the current job search, potentially enhancing their overall digital competency.

Potential Drawbacks

- 1. Competition and Oversaturation:** Because it's so simple to apply for jobs online, more

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people are doing so, which has boosted competitiveness and the number of applications that businesses receive. This may lead to oversaturation, which will make it difficult for individual applications to stand out and may aggravate job seekers.

2. Lack of Personalization: Online apps might not have the same level of personalization that can be found in more conventional techniques, including networking events or in-person encounters. The candidate's capacity to demonstrate their soft talents and leave a lasting impression on employers may be hampered by this impersonal character.

3. Limited Visibility for Non-Digital Roles: While online job portals are useful for office- and digital-based roles, they might not be as useful for jobs that call for specialized or hands-on abilities. There may not be as much representation for certain occupations on internet platforms, such as manual labour or the creative arts

4. Quality of Listings: It's possible for some job portals to host listings that are unreliable, deceptive, or even fraudulent. To make sure that the positions they apply for are genuine and in line with their expectations, job searchers should use prudence and practice due diligence.

Conclusion

E-recruitment is another term for online recruiting. In our country, reputable employment portals like monster.com, nakuri.com, shine.com, and numerous networking sites are accessible to help employers and employees with the hiring and selection procedures. The procedure is quite easy to understand for both the person and the business. E-recruitment has several advantages, including the capacity to move more rapidly, convenience of use, reduced administrative costs and manpower, and increased competency on the part of the company and personnel. For those who are directly or indirectly involved in the e-recruitment process and who are employed as HR personnel within the company, this study is highly helpful. A flawless answer is required for everything in the fast-paced, accuracy-focused world of today. In a similar vein, the recruitment process has become more efficient and time-saving thanks to the employment of highly sophisticated technologies. According to the study, job portals have a beneficial effect on employee performance since they make it simple to grow in your career and find decent jobs with competitive pay. The job platform also offers expert coaching and

knowledge of potential future career paths. Undoubtedly, the concept of job portals has gained popularity as a preferred means of recruitment for both job seekers and employers, but its efficiency and ability to meet job seekers' expectations is what will make it the ideal platform for recruiting.

References

- Ahlawat, R., & Sangeeta E-recruitment: Transforming trends of recruitment in Human resource management, *Global journal of Engineering Science and Research Management*, 3(1), 21–25. (2016).
- Amusan, D.G., Oyediran, M.O., Development of efficient e-recruitment system for university staff in Nigeria, *Circulation in computer science*, 1(1), 10-14. (2016). *International Journal of Management, Technology And Engineering* Volume 8, Issue XI, NOVEMBER/2018 ISSN NO : 2249-7455 Page No:1564
- Anand. J., Chitra Devi, S., Literature review on e-recruitment and its perceived benefits: A walk towards paperless HR, *International journal of applied research*, 2(11), 528-531. (2016).
- Chauhan. D., Chaturvedi. L., Efficacy of job portals and social media on organizational business, *international journal of advanced research in management and social sciences*, 2(7), 170-181. (2013).
- Edwin B Flippo (1984) *personnel management*, sixth edition-Hill International Edition, Management series.
- Faliagka, E., Tsakalidis, A., & Tzimas, G. An investigated e-recruitment system for automated personality mining and applicant ranking, *internet research*, 22(5), 551-568. (2012).
- Fred and Kinange (2016). *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*
- Galanaki. E (2002) "The decision to recruit online: a descriptive study", *Career Development International* vol. 7 No 7. 4, pp 243-251. <http://doi.org/10.1108/13620430210431325>.
- Mansourvar, M., Mohd Yasin, B. N., Development of a job web portal to improve education quality, *International journal of computer theory and engineering*, 6(1), 43-46. (2014).
- Nasreem, S., Hussan, M., & Khan, T.A. effectiveness of e-recruitment in small and medium enterprises of IT industry of lahore (Pakistan), *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 54(1), 143–164. (2016)
- Nasreen, Sidra, et al. "effectiveness of e-recruitment in small and medium enterprises of it industry of Lahore (Pakistan)." *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, vol. 54, no. 1, 2016, pp. 143–64. *JSTOR*, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26616703>. Accessed 12 Oct. 2022.
- Parry, E. and Wilson, H. (2009), *Factors Influencing the adoption of online recruitment*.

Personnel Review.

Rakholiya, N.& Gupta, C. A study on the Applicant' s Perception towards E-recruitment, International Multidisciplinary Journal of Applied Research, 1(1), 50–53. (2013)

Ramaabaanu, R. & Saranya, M. Importance and problems of e-recruitment, international journal of research, 1(9), 445-450. (2014) International Journal of Management, Technology and Engineering Volume 8, Issue XI, NOVEMBER/2018 ISSN NO: 2249- 7455 Page No:1566

Rani. R., E-recruitment and its impact upon on job seekers: A contemporary approach, IJARIE,2(4), 335-339. (2016).

Sherkar, A. A Study on Use of E- Resources in Recruitment and Selection Process in 5 Star Hotels, Atithya: A Journal of Hospitality,1(1),15-19. (2015).

Sylva, H., & Mol, S.T. E-recruitment: A study into applicant perceptions of an online application system, international journal of selection and assessment,17(3),311-323. (2009).